

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CLASSIFICATION OF THE CAUSES OF COLLECTOR DESTRUCTION AND SAND REMOVAL

Abatbayev A.

Petroleum Engineering

Oil and Gas Faculty

Atyrau University of Oil and Gas named after Safi Utebayev

Abstract

The article discusses the causes and classification of the causes of the destruction of the collector and the removal of sand. To maintain the level of oil production, it is necessary to increase the flow rates of wells, which inevitably leads to high filtration rates, contributing to the disruption and removal of mechanical impurities from weakly cemented reservoirs of the bottom-hole zone due to the destruction of the collector skeleton on the walls of channels and cracks due to the formation of microcracks. In this case, the process of destruction of the reservoir will be continuous due to the constant removal of particles of destroyed rock into the well.

Keywords: Well, bottom-hole zone, reservoir, electric centrifugal pump, hydraulic fracturing, geological and technical measures.

Perhaps the intensification of these processes explains the frequently occurring effect – increased removal of the concentration of suspended particles (EHF) at bottom-hole pressure below the saturation pressure. The nature of the origin of solid particles in pumping equipment is diverse. Their main share consists of particles removed from the formation during the operation of wells, but at the same time a significant part of mechanical impurities is of non-plastic origin: corrosion products of underground equipment and particles introduced into the well as a result of repairs and geological and technical measures; insoluble solid inclusions in the composition of the silencing fluid or proppant fragments after hydraulic fracturing, as well

as products formed by the interaction of chemically incompatible pumped liquids. The percentage composition of mechanical impurities contained in the production of wells is determined by the predominance of particles of formation origin (Table 1.) [1].

A classification of the causes of reservoir destruction and sand removal is proposed by dividing them into three main groups based on the conditions of occurrence:

- 1) geological (features of reservoir formation, lithology)
- 2) technological (conditions of formation opening and well operation)
- 3) technical (face design).

Table 1

Classification of causes of collector failure and sand removal

Природа Происхождения	Доля в Процентах	Состав частиц	Доля в Процентах
Пластовое	50-60	Магнитные и железные частицы	25-65
Смешанное (пластово-поверхностное)	15-25	Минеральные частицы из пласта	20-25
Поверхностное	10-20	Поверхностные частицы	10-50

Geological: the depth of the formation and reservoir pressure; the horizontal component of the rock pressure; the degree of cementation of the formation rock, its compaction and natural permeability; the nature of the extracted fluid and its phase state; characteristics of the formation sand (angularity, clay); the introduction of plantar waters into the deposit and dissolution of the cementing material; the duration of sand removal.

Technological: well flow rate; the magnitude of repression and depression on the formation; deterioration of natural permeability (skin effect); filtration loads and violation of capillary adhesion of sand.

Technical: the design of the face; the face surface through which filtration occurs (the interval of opening the formation, the perforation channels are open or clogged, etc.).

Among the main factors determining the concentration of impurities, the following are traditionally distinguished: the depth of the formation and reservoir pressure; reservoir permeability; physico-chemical properties of the extracted liquid; water content; characteristics of sand particles; well flow rate; perforation density; depression; type of working fluid used in the process of repair and restoration work [2].

The influence of mechanical mixtures on the operation of deep-pumping equipment. Mechanical impurities entering the rod pump significantly affect the performance of the plunger and valve pairs. Sand causes catastrophic wear of threaded connections of pumping pipes – at the slightest leakiness of the connections, especially in flooded wells, it quickly corrodes the thread and liquid flows through the formed channel, reducing the supply, and later leads to its complete termination.

The presence of a large amount of poorly permeable sediments at the bottom of the well primarily leads to a decrease in the flow rate of the liquid, because the concentrated mixture in the well increases the back pressure on the bottom and worsens the conditions of natural fluid inflow. Technical or technological shut-downs of wells contribute to the deposition of sand on the face and the formation of traffic jams, which is often the most serious problem in the operation of sand wells. When sand is deposited in the tubing, the pump jams, as a rule, when the downhole equipment stops. Field experience shows that the overwhelming number of plunger jamming occurs even with relatively short-term stops, for 10 to 20 minutes. This is due to the fact that the deposition of sand in the tubing begins immediately as soon as the pump has stopped, unlike the conditions for the formation of a plug at the bottom, where deposition does not begin immediately, since the inflow from the reservoir continues for some time after the withdrawal of fluid from the well has stopped. Prolonged pump stops are accompanied by the formation of a large number of solid sedimentary inclusions above the pump (up to 20 m in height). At the same time, the plunger in the pump cylinder and the rods in the pipes sometimes jam. Studies show that with a large amount of precipitation in the extracted liquid, the plunger itself may not lose mobility during pump operation, but due to the formation of a high column of sand and a large friction force against the walls of pipes and the surface of the rods, the column of rods may become stationary. In pipe pumps, when trying to move the plunger from its place up, it will immediately jam in the cylinder due to the ingress of sand into the gap and a sharp increase in the friction forces of the plunger in the cylinder, even without strong scuffing of the working surfaces. A similar pattern is observed with a plug-in pump, when due to the sediment of sand it is not possible to tear it from the landing ring. When the plunger is jammed or the plug-in pump is seized, the rods and pipes have to be lifted together, which causes complications in underground repairs. In practice, during scheduled stops, it is necessary to ensure the upper extreme position of the plunger, which corresponds to the upper extreme position of the balancer head, so that during the start, the rod column and the plunger make a downward stroke [2].

The phenomena of plug formation in wells and the effect of sand on the underground part of the pumping unit are interrelated: a decrease or termination of the pump supply due to rapid wear of working pairs of equipment, erosion of pipe connections, etc. causes the formation of a plug at the bottom. Therefore, the root cause of the termination of the fluid supply is not the formation of a plug at the bottom of the well, but the wear of pumping equipment.

Complications during the output of the well to the regime are due to the high content of EHF in the initial period of operation after underground repair or hydraulic fracturing (fracking) – from 200 to 1000 mg/l [3]. This often exceeds the passport characteristics of pumps, even of wear-resistant design. Mechanical particles passing through the working bodies of the SR produce abrasive work, are the main cause of jamming

of plungers in the cylinder, breakage of rods, failure of valve pairs, clog the pump filter.

According to Shashkin M.A. [2] in many newly developed pumping wells, a significant amount of mechanical impurities comes from the reservoir only in the first days of operation. The bulk of failures of deep-pumping equipment for clogging – about 80%, falls on newly introduced wells from drilling, after drilling the second trunk, underground repairs and hydraulic fracturing. In the future, there are no failures due to clogging at these wells during the development of the well in a certain period of time [3,4].

The overflow of the perforation zone by the products of formation destruction occurs both immediately after hydraulic fracturing and repeatedly during operation. At the final stage of hydraulic fracturing, a certain amount of proppant, not injected into the formation of a wedging agent, necessarily remains in the wellbore. Its volume can range from hundreds of kilograms to dozens of tons. Normalization of the face before the pump is lowered is carried out by well overhaul teams, however, the removal of the proppant continues during further operation, which in case of equipment failure requires repeated work to normalize the face, which in turn increases the cost of cattle, well downtime and contamination of the bottom-hole zone. The overflow of the perforation zone of wells with a large sand removal is complicated by the fact that, as a rule, the fight against this phenomenon begins at a late stage of well operation, when the bottom-hole zone is already heavily drained and frequent plug formation is observed. At the same time, it is known that work on strengthening the bottom-hole zone at the stage of completion of wells after drilling gives the best results [4].

Methods of combating sand manifestation. The solution to the problem of combating the removal of sand into the borehole is associated with the need to prevent plug formation during testing and operation of wells, increase their productivity, reduce the cost of capital and maintenance repairs.

The study of many years of commercial experience in combating sand occurrence has shown that the most rational ways to combat sand removal are the following methods, which can be divided into two groups:

- installation of filters of various designs (wire, slit, gravel, etc.);
- consolidation of rocks in the bottom-hole zone using various methods and materials (grouting compounds, resins, chemical solutions, etc.).

It should be noted that in some cases sand formation can also play a positive role in the case of exploitation of low-power layers composed of low-permeable rocks. Removal of sand and particles of destroyed rocks from such layers leads to an increase in the permeability of the bottom-hole zone and, as a result, to an increase in the flow rate of the well. From this point of view, the methods of operation of wells with sand occurrence are divided into two broad groups:

- operation of wells with sand removal to the surface;
- operation of wells to prevent the removal of sand from the reservoir.

Figure 1.2 shows the main methods of operation of wells with sand manifolds.

Figure 1.2 - Methods of operation of wells with sand manifolds

When choosing a method of combating sand removal, temperature restrictions are taken into account. For chemical methods, the permissible temperature limits are 16-175 °C, for mechanical methods there are no such restrictions, except when oil or thickened solutions are used in the formation of gaskets.

The technological methods of preventing sand occurrence in wells include, first of all, the regulation of fluid sampling from the well. At the same time, the viscosity of the fluid in reservoir conditions has a certain value. The higher the viscosity of the fluid, the smaller the pressure gradient can be critical, that is, the one at which the removal of sand begins.

Gas has a significantly lower viscosity than water or, especially, heavy resinous oil. Therefore, a gas reservoir composed of weakly cemented sandstones may be subjected to more significant depressions, therefore, during the development of a gas field, as the gas is withdrawn, the water-bearing contour is tightened or the plantar water rises, so that the water approaches the production gas well and, eventually, enters the bottom. If the sandstone is cemented with clay or calcareous material, then the water as it is taken from the well

gradually washes out this material, contributing to the destruction of the formation even at lower depressions than initially[5].

References

1. Butko O.G., Skuin B.A. Methods of combating sand phenomena during the operation of oil wells // VNIIOENG. Ser. Oilfield business. 1987.-No. 3.
2. Smolnikov S.V. et al. Methods of protection of pumping equipment for oil production from mechanical impurities. Ufa: Oil and gas business, 2010. 41 p.
3. Schmidt A.A. Improving the efficiency of wells operation complicated by the content of mechanical impurities in products: abstract of the dissertation of the Candidate of Technical Sciences. Ufa, 2007. 25 p.
4. Kazakov D.P. Improving the efficiency of well operation by electric centrifugal pumps after hydraulic fracturing: abstract of the dissertation. Candidate of Technical Sciences, Ufa, 2010. 26 p.
5. Shashkin M.A. Protection methods used in the Langepasneftegaz CCI to reduce the negative impact of mechanical impurities on the work of the GNR // Engineering practice. 2010. No. 2. pp. 26-31.